

Title Page

California Cropland Carbon Monitoring and modeling framework

RFP number: 23ISD006

Date: March 22, 2024

Proposer: Pools and Fluxes LLC

Contact: Chris Black

chris@poolsandfluxes.com

503 929 9421

Cover Letter / Letter of Commitment

Pools and Fluxes, LLC
chris@poolsandfluxes.com / 503 929 9421
5275 Calle Cristobal, Santa Barbara CA 93111
CA Entity no. 202461114541

22 March, 2024

To Whom it may Concern,

On behalf of a consortium of ecosystem scientists, carbon monitoring researchers, and software developers, I am pleased to submit this proposal for a California Cropland Monitoring and Modeling Framework. Our proposed system builds on a proven ecological modeling and forecasting framework (PEcAn, the **Predictive Ecosystem Analyzer**) that is mature, widely used, provides consistent best-in-class handling of all aspects of uncertainty, and is backed by an active user community and many years of successful open-source development. It will be coupled to a simple biogeochemistry model updated specifically for this project, and driven by statewide, ongoing, freely available satellite data to enable principled data assimilation of carbon stocks and greenhouse gas fluxes across all CA cropland. We believe this system will enable uniform, reproducible, statistically sound monitoring that exceeds the stated requirements and is easily extensible for your future needs.

Our team has broad and deep expertise developing and deploying modeling systems and climate change monitoring, a well-tested productive working relationship, and access to computing resources and expertise from NASA, Boston University, and the National Center for Supercomputing Applications. We are eager to start building for you!

The contact person for this proposal is Chris Black, chris@poolsandfluxes.com, 503 929 9421. Please get in touch if you need any other information.

The enclosed proposal is submitted in response to the above referenced Request for Proposal 23ISD006, including any addenda. Through submission of this proposal, we agree to all of the terms and conditions of the Request for Proposal and agree that any inconsistent provisions in our proposal may result in a lower score, up to and including disqualification. We have carefully read and examined the Request for Proposal and have conducted such other investigations as were prudent and reasonable in preparing the proposal. We agree to be bound by statements and representations in our proposal.

Sincerely,

Christopher K Black, President
Pools and Fluxes LLC

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Summary

In response to the California Air Resources Board's Request for Proposals (RFP No 23ISD006), Our team presents a comprehensive approach to developing the California Cropland Carbon Monitoring and Modeling Framework. Our team brings extensive experience and are leaders in the fields of biogeochemical modeling, remote sensing, computing, and ecological forecasting. We propose to build on existing tools to build an advanced system that integrates this expertise to quantify carbon stocks and greenhouse gas emissions across California's cropland ecosystems.

The foundation of our approach is the Predictive Ecosystem Analyzer (PEcAn), which is already being used by NASA's Carbon Monitoring System for continental scale terrestrial carbon cycle reanalysis, and by the Finnish Meteorological Institute for carbon inventories in agricultural systems. We will expand the functionality of the simplified biogeochemistry model SIPNET to simulate agricultural systems including management, nitrogen cycling, and methane production. We will develop new remote sensing algorithms to monitor management of croplands including planting, tillage, cover crops, land use change, harvest, and irrigation. These improvements will allow estimation of carbon stocks and GHG emissions as well as ensemble forecasting to predict the impact of climate scenarios as well as scenarios related to the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices.

Key features of our proposal include:

Remote sensing: The project will use data from multiple satellites to monitor crop management practices, and produce monitoring datasets that can be used by biogeochemical models to simulate the responses of croplands to sustainable management practices.

Process-Based Ecosystem Modeling: We will enhance SIPNET functionality to include processes that control GHG fluxes and represent agricultural management.

Model-Data Synthesis: Within the PEcAn framework, we will synthesize heterogeneous data and quantify uncertainty to not only provide the best available inventories and forecasts, but also identify data to collect and improvements to model structure for efficient uncertainty reduction.

Ecological Forecasting: We will also predict responses of agricultural carbon stocks and GHG emissions to future climate and cropland management scenarios. This will enable decision makers to explore opportunities to increase carbon sequestration and reduce greenhouse gas emissions across California's croplands.

Open Science: The team are open science advocates with long histories of developing open source software, open data, and training scientists in reproducible research. We believe that the transparency, accessibility, and reusability of ecosystem monitoring infrastructure is essential to advancing the CARB's goals of quantifying carbon sequestration and mitigating GHG emissions.

Minimum Qualifications Response

Please see Attachment 12 for resumes from all personnel.

Knowledge and experience in remote sensing of ecosystem change and state

Serbin is our remote sensing expert. His experience includes:

- NASA TE project on hyperspectral assimilation
- NASA Carbon Monitoring System CMS project assimilating MODIS, Landsat, SMAP, and GEDI
- NASA HypsIRI and NASA SBG scientist
- Developed and maintained UAS program focused on terrestrial ecosystem structure, function and change
- Active in NASA ABoVE and was the liason between DOE NGEA-Arctic and NASA ABoVE
- Skilled in the use of AVIRIS-Classic, AVIRIS-NG and NEON AOP, and G-LiHT data for the study of plant functioning
- Over 20 years of experience with spectroscopy, imaging spectroscopy, disturbance detection and mapping, and the use of passive/active optical, infrared, and radar systems for ecosystem science
- Lab Chief of the Goddard Biospheric Sciences Laboratory focused on the study of coastal and terrestrial ecosystem dynamics using remote sensing and modeling

Dietze also has deep experience with remote sensing, including

- NASA TE project on hyperspectral assimilation
- NASA CMS project assimilating MODIS, Landsat, SMAP, and GEDI
- Multiple publications using NOAA GOES geostationary platform, including algorithm development on modeling the diurnal cycle of NDVI (Wheeler and Dietze, 2019, 2021)
- Student's in Dietze's lab have been trained by members of BU's Center for Remote Sensing, a leading center in the field and producer of half of the MODIS land products and the GLANCE landsat land cover product

LeBauer's experience with proximate sensing is relevant

- His role as leader of the data and computing pipeline for TERRA-REF, a 1 PB public domain dataset including hyperspectral, thermal, laser scan, RGB, and PSII fluorescence plant imaging, alongside genomic and trait data to support crop breeding.
- Experience developing pipelines for UAS data and building community around open source data, protocols, software, and standards for the use of UAS for plot based crop breeding trials and experiments.

Knowledge and experience in process-based ecosystem modeling towards estimation of carbon stocks and greenhouse gas fluxes;

- Black has used DayCent extensively for modeling of carbon stocks and CO₂ fluxes (Black *et al.*, 2017; Mathers *et al.*, 2023)
- LeBauer, Black, and Longfritz worked at Indigo Ag, the first producer verified, registry-issued soil carbon credits at scale for farmers adopting sustainable practices.
- Estimating carbon stocks from process-based models has been a central theme of PEcAn since its inception (Dietze, Lebauer and Kooper, 2013; LeBauer *et al.*, 2013). The PEcAn team includes Dietze, LeBauer, Kooper, and Black. The PEcAn community has coupled >20 process-based ecosystem models to the PEcAn system.
- Dietze has been a member of the Ecosystem Demography Model version 2 (ED2) development team since 2006 and the Functionally Assembled Terrestrial Ecosystem Simulator (FATES) development team since 2016.
- Dietze and Serbin have been members of NASA's Carbon Monitoring System team since 2016. Serbin is co-chair of the CMS uncertainty working group.
- Serbin has been active in the development of FATES, and has worked with and utilized a range of other models including DVM-DOS-TEM, CLM, ELM, SIPNET and ED2. He has published with these models, and has added new features and participated other model development activities.
- LeBauer has been an active developer and user of the BioCro crop model and has used ED2, SIPNET, and CLM to estimate carbon stocks.

Knowledge and experience in cropland projects, their management, and California's healthy soils program or the United States Department of Agriculture's Climate Smart Agricultural practices;

- Black and LeBauer have worked primarily in cropland systems throughout their careers, with research themes consistently investigating the ecological effects of management decisions.
- Black, LeBauer, and Longfritz all worked on carbon crediting models at Indigo Ag, with connection of agricultural management data to model inputs a central theme.
- Black participated in planning and implementation of Indigo Ag's partnership in the USDA Partnerships for Climate Smart Commodities program.
- Dietze has served as IME for numerous Verra and CAR agricultural soil C projects and was formerly a UIUC professor working on biofuel agriculture
- Serbin worked across a range of agricultural systems in California during the NASA HyspIRI campaign, publishing multiple studies on the upscaling of carbon fluxes and links with crop health and status.
- Serbin has also worked on a host of ag-related projects focused on early warning and stress detection, analysis of climate records and modeling of climate change impacts on cropping systems in the midwest, and developing methods for the monitoring of crop stress with proximal to spaceborne sensing systems.

Knowledge and experience working with statewide scale or larger temporal and spatial data and models;

- With support from Kooper, LeBauer led in the TERRA REF data and computing team, 1PB crop multi-sensor, trait and genomic dataset (Burnette *et al.*, 2018)
- Dietze and Serbin CMS2016 (CONUS) and CMS2020 (North American) C cycle reanalysis (model-data fusion) project
- Dietze was a member, and former chair, of NEON's science advisory committee. Serbin is a current member. Dietze was also on NASA's DAAC Advisory Board
- Serbin studied climate change impacts on cropping systems in Wisconsin using state-wide and regional climate data and agricultural statistics
- Serbin is also a co-lead of the Arctic Systems Interactions priority area of the Interagency Arctic Research Policy Council (IARPC).
- Kooper is involved with the systems of Permafrost Discovery Gateway (Liljedahl *et al.*, 2019). This processes and uses high resolution satellite imagery to monitor thaw of permafrost across the arctic.

Knowledge and experience in future projection modeling incorporating global climate model data to estimate changes in ecosystem function and state;

- LeBauer has forecasted Sugarcane (Jaiswal *et al.*, 2017), Agave (Davis, Abatzoglou and LeBauer, 2021) productivity under future climate scenarios.
- Black forecasts of SOC change in corn-soybean under future climate scenarios (Black *et al.*, 2017; Mathers *et al.*, 2023)).
- Dietze is author of the book "Ecological Forecasting" (Dietze, 2017a), the first and only book explicitly on prediction and data assimilation for ecologists and biogeoscientists.
- Serbin conducted research into the forecasting of future climate change impacts on cropping systems in Wisconsin for the Wisconsin Initiative on Climate Change Impacts (WICCI) and created a gridded climate product that is still in use for this effort.

Experience developing tools, models, data pipelines, or products for practical applications for clients other than the developers themselves;

- PEcAn is a mature (~15 year) open-source, multi-stakeholder project with 84 developers, ~22,000 commits, 2300 downloads, and 32 tagged version releases
- Black and LeBauer validated ecosystem models at Indigo, following externally specified requirements and subject to third-party review and verification.
- Longfritz has developed systems and tools for industry, government, and scientific clients
 - Software lead for large-scale synthetic terrain data fusion and modeling for multi-company DARPA projects
 - Architect for military command forces simulations for DARPA projects
 - Lead architect for multiple projects at Mathworks across the MATLAB and Simulink tool chains
 - Developed and implemented algorithms for fast and efficient distribution of world-wide resources for internet traffic caching and mapping

- Kooper is Lead Research Software Engineer for the Software Design Delivery and Deploy team at NCSA, which develops a variety of software to support scientific research including PEcAn and TERRA-REF
- LeBauer's Data Science Support team at the University of Arizona provided software, data science, and computing support for the College of Agriculture and Life Sciences
- Dietze and Serbin are members of NASA's Carbon Monitoring System, with Serbin as co-lead of the Uncertainty working group. Dietze has also provided numerous independent model reviews for the CAR and Verra voluntary C markets, serves on the Environmental Defense Fund's soil C market expert working group, and was a COP28 observer for the Ecological Society of America, focused on C markets.
- Serbin also created a data pipeline and data standards for UAS datasets collected as part of the larger DOE NGEE-Arctic project that are still used by that project.

Experience working across disciplines and within large teams;

- Black participated in international collaborative benchmarking of root models with >20 co-authors including mathematicians, computer scientists, hydrologists, soil scientists, and multiple flavors of biologist (Schnepf *et al.*, 2020, 2023)
- Dietze has considerable experience managing projects this size and larger, having served as lead PI on 17 previous grants, and co-PI on 12 grants, 17 of which were comparable in size (\$0.5-2.0M) to the current proposal and four of which were larger and more complex (\$10M, \$5M, \$4M, \$2.5M).
- Dietze is founder and chair of the Ecological Forecasting Initiative, an interdisciplinary, international community of practice with four international chapters and >1000 participants.
- LeBauer has experience with projects of comparable size within diverse interdisciplinary projects including as manager of the Energy Biosciences Institute ecosystem modeling program representing four PIs and three ecosystem modeling teams, lead of the data and computing pipeline team and Co-PI on ARPA-E funded TERRA REF project, lead of the ecophysiology and ecosystem dynamics modeling team and co-PI on the SENTINEL team of a DARPA Advancing Plant Technologies project, and founder and lead of the University of Arizona CCT Data Science team.
- Serbin is a current member of the NEON STEAC and a co-lead of the Arctic Systems Interactions priority area of the Interagency Arctic Research Policy Council (IARPC). He led the collaboration between NASA ABoVE and DOE NGEE-Arctic including helping to coordinate airborne campaigns, and helped coordinate the airborne campaigns during the NASA HyspIRI project in California. He has been part of both DOE NGEE projects that span across 5 National Labs, NASA and Universities (both national and international). He is the Goddard lead for the NASA SBG mission and liaison with lead institution NASA JPL. He is co-lead of the DOE Atmospheric Radiation Measurement (ARM) campaign in the Southeastern US (AMF3-BNF). He is also the Lab Chief of the Biospheric Sciences Laboratory at NASA Goddard Space Flight Center which employees over 100 Civil Servants, cooperative scientists contractors, students and postdocs

- Kooper is a part of the software directorate at NCSA, a group of over 40 research software engineers that work on many different projects. Kooper is the lead of a team of 7 people that work on different projects in NCSA. Some of these projects deal with hazards in different locations in the USA (such as tornado, and earthquakes).
- Longfritz has worked on multi-company DARPA programs, often as a lead engineer, including writing requirements and design docs, preparing status updates, demoing products and writing final reports.
- Longfritz served as lead architect for several multi-team initiatives at Mathworks for both MATLAB and Simulink, including defining initial requirements and design, managing intra- and inter-team communications, and organizing teams of up to ten developers.

Experience in incorporating equity and environmental justice into science and/or policy development.

- Dietze is chair of the DEI committee for BU's Department of Earth & Environment, a >30 person committee with membership spanning all aspects of the department (undergrads, grads, postdocs, staff, faculty). In this role he has coordinated the following efforts:
 - Baseline surveys of departmental demographics and climate
 - Admissions and hiring guidelines
 - Developed departmental infographics explaining how to report different types of issues (discrimination, sexual assault, etc)
 - Ran an undergraduate orientation focused on equity, inclusion, and retention
 - Compiled departmental field safety resources and developed code of conduct for research and classes
 - Compiled a "resource map" for incoming members of our community to help everyone be able to navigate departmental resources, not just those "in the know"
 - Compiled guidelines for working with communities of color and providing land acknowledgements
 - Runs an annual screening and discussion around "Picture a Scientist", a documentary on inequalities faced by women in science, which uses a past incident in my own department as a major example (~1/3 of the film).
- The Ecological Forecasting Initiative has been leading a training and mentoring program focused on inclusive and culturally-relevant education in environmental data science for undergraduates from traditionally underrepresented groups, with a particular focus on Native American students. This program is supported by the Alfred P. Sloan foundation (Dietze co-I) and co-produced with educators at three MSIs, including Cal Poly Humboldt, and AIHEC (the American Indian Higher Education Consortium)
- LeBauer created and administered a scholarship to support North American Plant Phenotyping Network conference attendance by HBCU participants, wrote an article on increasing racial diversity at conferences (LeBauer *et al.*, 2023) and received the 2023 EID award from NAPPN.

- As manager of the mushroom lab at NC A&T, a HBCU, LeBauer worked with NC extension to distribute mushroom spawn and train diverse and small landholder farmers across NC in sustainable forest management and shiitake production.
- Serbin has mentored a wide-range of staff, students, researchers, and postdocs from a variety of backgrounds and experiences. At DOE he mentored numerous undergraduate students through the SULI program and was actively involved in the development of DEIA initiatives and Codes of Conduct for projects and his group. He has actively fostered collaborations with MSIs and HBCUs in Alabama, worked with tribal communities, and is working to build connections with underserved communities in the Washington DC region through Citizen Science activities.

Personnel and Experience

Overview

Our team has extensive demonstrated experience enabling and advancing research through **open science** advocacy, development of **open software and data**, and through training of the next generation of scientists. The team has extensive experience in the development and application of **crop and biogeochemical models** to estimate and predict carbon (C) and greenhouse gas (GHG) fluxes.

Mike Dietze

Dr. Michael Dietze (Co-I) has been the PI of the PEcAn project since its inception in 2009. Dr. Dietze also has extensive expertise in ecosystem ecology, vegetation modeling, statistics, and model-data fusion, all highly relevant topics to this proposal. He is a leader in the field of Ecological Forecasting as evidenced by his text book “Ecological Forecasting”, leadership of the Ecological Forecasting Initiative, and other research activities.

Dietze has been part of the NASA CMS team Uncertainty working group, where he has contributed extensive experience with model-data fusion, uncertainty analysis, process-based modeling, and Bayesian statistics. Dietze has worked closely with the modeling community for over 20 years, specializing on the interface between models and data as a way to better understand and forecast the carbon cycle. As founder and director of the Ecological Forecasting Initiative (ecoforecast.org) and author of the book “Ecological Forecasting”, Dietze has been a vocal advocate for near-term iterative ecological forecasting as a means of both advancing basic science and making ecology more decision relevant. Finally, Dietze has served as an Independent Modeling Expert in the Verra and CAR voluntary carbon markets, where he has certified numerous project accreditation reports. Dietze will lead Task 1: Conceptual Framework Development and Task 3: Monitoring Framework Development. Dietze is assigned 480 hours and will supervise a student who will be assigned 1920 hours on the project.

Chris Black

Dr. Christopher K. Black has more than a decade of experience in ecosystem modeling and greenhouse gas quantification. As president of Pools and Fluxes LLC, he provides consulting and model development services focused on validation of ecosystem models for commercial and policy applications. As a Senior Scientist at Indigo Ag, he led validation of DayCent-CR for carbon crediting under the Climate Action Reserve's Soil Enrichment protocol. As a researcher at the Pennsylvania State University Roots Lab, he designed and implemented soil physics modules for an open-source model of root architecture and participated in collaborative worldwide cross-model benchmarking activities. As a contributor and organization administrator to the PEcAn project since 2017, he focuses on code quality and integration testing initiatives and mentors student contributors through the Google Summer of Code program. Black will lead Task 4: Communication of Scientific Results, serve as Contract Manager and Administrative Contact, and lead model Task 2.5: Model Calibration and Validation. He will be assigned to the Agreement for 2000 hours.

David LeBauer

Dr. David LeBauer worked with Dr. Dietze to implement the initial PEcAn workflows and has continued as a collaborator, contributor, mentor and community facilitator. Dr. LeBauer has worked extensively with crop, ecosystem, and biogeochemical models. He has advocated for open science principles and in addition to PEcAn has published open data sets including the Biofuel Ecophysiological Traits and Yields database (BETYdb) that serves as PEcAn's informatics backbone and the TERRA REF reference plant phenotyping data set, producing over 1 PB of crop sensing, trait, and gene sequence data for the public domain. He has further enabled scientific computing as Director of Data Science at the University of Arizona and as a mentor and Carpentries Instructor. At Indigo Ag (2023-2024), Dr. LeBauer worked with Dr. Black to calibrate and validate a biogeochemical model of soil carbon and greenhouse gas fluxes. LeBauer will serve as project manager and lead Task 2: Modeling Framework and Task 2.5: Model Uncertainty Analysis. He will be assigned to the Agreement for 2000 hours.

Mike Longfritz

Dr. Michael J. Longfritz has several decades of professional software engineering experience. He has spent significant time architecting, designing, implementing and testing in the areas of military simulations for DARPA, scientific computing tools for science and engineering, and large-scale distributed systems. As a Principal Software Engineer at Indigo Ag, he worked on several aspects of the company's carbon crediting pipeline, including implementing extensions to the suite of biogeochemical models as well as improving, testing, and validating the pipeline infrastructure. Dr. Longfritz will lead Task 2.3: Model Implementation and will be assigned to the Agreement for 456 hours,

Rob Kooper

Rob Kooper has multiple decades of experience with software development and software deployment. He is a lead Research Software Engineer with the Software Development Directorate at the National Center for Supercomputing Applications, where he is one of the main architects of many of their software projects, and more specifically of their deployment. He has extensive experience with optimizations for both cloud and HPC use of these deployments. He has overseen the software deployment aspects of PEcAn since its early days, moving the project from a single HPC to its current docker and cloud architecture that can be, and is, deployed all over the world. Kooper is responsible for subtasks throughout the project related to k. Kooper is assigned to the Agreement for 400 hours.

Shawn Serbin

Dr. Serbin has been a member of the PEcAn team since 2011. Dr. Serbin brings extensive experience at the interface between remote sensing and plant physiological ecology, as well a background in process-based modeling and model-data assimilation. Serbin was previously Co-I on DOE's NGEE Tropics and Arctic projects, which focused on improving carbon cycle models and projections in these two critical biomes, prior to moving to NASA, and was co-lead of the NASA Surface Biology and Geology (SBG) modeling working group and SBG Modeling End-to-End Traceability effort. He is currently a funded SBG scientist. He is also involved in the U.S. Greenhouse Gas Center, working on using surface networks and remote sensing to scale processes and benchmark models and is a member of the Decadal Survey Incubator for a Planetary Boundary Layer mission. Serbin will work closely with the team to advise on both modeling and monitoring activities and to synergize with related research. Serbin is assigned to the Agreement 0 hours.

Technical Portion

Background

Here we propose to implement a "California Cropland Carbon Monitoring and Modeling Framework" in response to the California Air Resources Board Request for Proposals 23ISD006. Our goal is to produce new datasets based on **monitoring the adoption of sustainable agronomic practices** as well as **C stock** and **GHG flux inventories** and **scenario based forecasts**

This proposal is structured around four components, all designed and documented for reuse and extensibility: A novel **simplified biogeochemistry model**, **a modeling framework** for uncertainty analysis, validation, and data synthesis, the creation and application of new

satellite-derived crop management practices, and the production of **statewide GHG inventories** under current (annually updated) and future climate and management scenarios. . Our implementation will be built on, and in synergy with, the project team's history of work in the measurement, modeling, and forecasting of biogeochemical and ecological dynamics of ecosystems including agricultural cropping systems.

This proposal includes improvement of the simplified biogeochemical model SIPNET to add support of GHG fluxes, and use of the improved model to estimate inventories and forecasts of C pools and GHG fluxes. The proposed work will build on and synergize with other ongoing projects, including the use of SIPNET in the NASA Carbon Monitoring System data assimilation framework (Dokoochaki *et al.*, 2021, 2022).

The modeling workflow and analysis will be built on the open-source PEcAn (Predictive Ecosystem Analyzer) modeling framework (Dietze, Lebauer and Kooper, 2013; LeBauer *et al.*, 2013). The project team has been developing and applying PEcAn as a cutting edge framework for ecosystem modeling and informatics for fifteen years. PEcAn supports model parameterization, uncertainty analysis, calibration, and data assimilation (these terms are explained under Methodology). It also provides tools required to manage data flows including model parameters, inputs, validation data, and data assimilation constraints - notably this includes handling and propagating component uncertainties. PEcAn works with a suite of >20 terrestrial ecosystem models and can synthesize data with different spatial and temporal resolutions, extents, and uncertainties. PEcAn is **used operationally by the Finnish Meteorological Institute to model the impacts of agricultural management impacts on cropland carbon budgets** (Nevalainen *et al.*, 2022). It also serves as the backbone for a similar system under development at the UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology (Cowdery and Yeluripati, 2022).

To support the prediction of agronomic management practices on the carbon balance and GHG impacts of California's croplands, we will combine a rich library of existing datasets with newly developed layers that track critical management practices, including tillage, planting and harvest, and historic land use.

A key component of the proposed work is a commitment to enabling research through open science. The team's history of open science work includes not only the creation of open software and data products, but also a commitment to reproducible research, community development, and training.

Management Plan

Our approach to management of the California Cropland Carbon Monitoring Project will be based on effective collaborations among the team among the team over the past fifteen years.

The team structure and project management will be based on experience and expertise in software development using agile, iterative development processes. The team has effectively worked well together, sharing the day-to-day tasks of project management and execution.

The contract manager will be Chris Black, who will also be the administrative contact for the project and responsible for communication of scientific results.

The project manager will be David LeBauer, who will be responsible for keeping the team on track with subtasks to ensure that milestones are met.

The project will be divided into three components, with a leader responsible for each component, and within each component, a project member responsible for each task and subtask. Members of the project team will collaborate across components, and each task will be a team collaboration. The conceptual framework (Task 1) will be led by Dietze, and implemented by the team. The modeling framework (Task 2) will be led by LeBauer. Within Task 2, the development and implementation of model calibration and validation will be led by Black, modeling workflow implementation and automation will be led by LeBauer, and model implementation will be led by Longfritz. The monitoring framework (Task 3) will be led by Dietze. Communication of scientific results (Task 4) will be led by Black, including presentations at scientific meetings, writing papers, and the final report.

Our management approach will follow a hierarchical agile approach that has been developed and refined by LeBauer over the last decade (Riemer *et al.*, 2024). The approach will include **methods to measure project progress against project management plan to maintain project schedule**. At the top of this hierarchy, the work plan defines the deliverables and milestones that provide project structure. Within the Work Schedule milestones, we will set objectives and key results that align with project milestones at three month intervals (Doerr, 2018). Within these quarterly cycles, we will use an agile approach with Scrum methodology and a cadence of two-week sprints. We will manage sprints using GitHub projects, and within sprints, we will keep track of individual tasks. Each pull request will be required to pass automated tests as well as be reviewed and approved by at least one other team member. All members of the project team have used GitHub projects for public tasks, pull requests, and milestones, as can be seen in the PEcAn project repository (github.com/pecanproject/pecan).

We have made every attempt to adequately consider contingencies, and we believe every component of this project has a high probability of success as proposed. However, portions of this project will involve development of novel scientific products, a process that is inherently unpredictable. When deviations from the scope, timeline, or risk profile of the project plan arise, we will evaluate them first for their scientific impact, then their timeline impact, then for the degree of change they require in other parts of the project. Framing milestones and subtasks as quarterly objectives and key results that we revisit each month, and using a two week agile scrum will facilitate communication and help identify deviations from our plan in a timely fashion.

This will maintain open communication of progress and allow the team to work together to minimize impacts. If a deviation becomes major enough to threaten the timeliness or quality of a deliverable, we will notify CARB promptly and work with CARB to develop an appropriate response. We understand and accept that our bid cannot be modified after submission, even in the case of deviations that increase the time or cost of the project.

Design documents will be collaborative, led by project component leads. Where possible all decisions will be made by consensus, but when disagreement remains the decision of the component lead will be final.

We currently use GitHub Actions as the foundation of our **software Quality Assurance** for the PEcAn project, and will implement similar Actions for the monitoring and modeling code repositories. Actions include defined workflows that automate the process of **building and testing** the software on every pull request. We will continue to expand our unit and integration testing suite for both the existing and newly developed features to defensively identify bugs and ensure confidence and correctness in the tested functionality. Any issues discovered through this process will be encapsulated as regression tests to prevent re-introduction of these issues.

Actions also provide automated labeling, templates, and updates for issues and pull requests. We will also set up a testing environment in which full system integration tests will run at least monthly during active development. The full integration test will re-run all steps in the pipeline from fetching the data all the way through the final analysis. This will help us ensure that we are on target with respect to meeting the model skill, and that the pipeline and its environment is correctly specified. We will implement a dashboard to track these tests and metrics including the time, resources used, and summaries of the results of each test run.

Additionally, we will take the models that are built and continuously run them on our test infrastructure. Unlike the full system integration tests, this will focus on just the models. During this testing we will not only validate the results but also see how the performance is doing and if we are on target to meet our goals to process all of the state. We will also implement automated reporting or dashboards that include summaries of both the computational performance (e.g. number of runs, CPUs, and time required) as well as scientific performance (e.g. maps and summaries of C stock and GHG flux inventories and forecasts).

Methodology (Approach to work)

Our approach will be to combine available information to generate the **most reliable C stock and GHG flux inventories and forecasts possible**. This information will come in the form of heterogeneous data, simulation models, and expert knowledge.

The core concept underlying the proposed monitoring system is that no single measurement provides a complete picture. Different remote sensing technologies, field observations, and

surveys each provide partial information about the carbon pools and greenhouse gasses associated with different crops and management practices. The challenge is that different data sources capture information at different spatiotemporal scales and with different amounts of uncertainty. Therefore, it is rarely straightforward, and often impossible, to directly combine or “fuse” these datasets to produce reasonable inventories of soil carbon and GHG emissions.

An alternative to directly combining datasets is to use **process-based models as a scaffold for data-driven synthesis**. This approach leverages the fact that mechanistic models explicitly represent the processes and scales represented in the data. Thus, we can use process-based models within a statistical framework as a means of linking data sources to generate a composite data product that contains significantly more information than the individual data sources. The approach, known as state-variable data assimilation, is conceptually different from traditional forward modeling, inverse modeling (using data that match model outputs to infer inputs), and calibration (using data that match outputs to infer parameters). While in common use in the atmospheric sciences, where it is a key component of numerical weather prediction (Kalnay, 2003; Lewis, Lakshminarayanan and Dhall, 2006), such approaches have had more limited application to terrestrial biogeochemical cycles (Fox *et al.*, 2018, 2022; Raiho *et al.*, 2020; Raczka *et al.*, 2021) despite enormous potential for C and GHG inventories.

At the center of our **Bayesian calibration, state estimation (inventory) and data assimilation** approach is the idea of the Forecast/Analysis Cycle (Figure 1). Consider a state variable, such as soil C stock, whose value we are interested in at a particular location or time, where the uncertainty about that state variable is represented by a probability distribution (1: Initial Conditions). The process-based biogeochemistry model SIPNET is then run numerous times using different samples representing initial condition, model driver, and parameter uncertainty to generate an ensemble forecast of the same state variable forward in time (2: Prior Inventory). Driver uncertainty is currently captured through the ensemble-based ERA5 meteorological re-analysis (Hersbach *et al.*, 2020), In this project, we will similarly estimate and propagate uncertainty in land use change and cropland management base on historical data and the new remote sensing based monitoring algorithms described below. As described in the Calibration section, parameter uncertainty will be estimated from data and expert knowledge. Parameter uncertainty is currently incorporated through a combination of prior specification and Bayesian meta-analysis of trait data (LeBauer *et al.*, 2013).

Figure 1: Proposed analysis workflow for C stock and GHG flux annual inventories and scenario based forecasting. Green elements represent final data products generated for CARB. Red numbers are referenced in adjacent proposal text to walk the reader through the proposed Forecast/Analysis cycle.

Prior to acquiring new observations our model forecast is our best estimate of the state of the system, but using Bayes' Theorem we can update this prior estimate based on new data (and their observation uncertainties) in two ways. We can assimilate data to update the system state, which then serves as the initial state for further projections (Dietze, 2017a). This statistical updating is often referred to as the Analysis step, and the total uncertainty in the Analysis will be lower than that from either the model or the data alone. Precise data, when present, will dictate the Analysis update while noisy data, by contrast, will contribute what information it contains without overwhelming the model into producing noisy or physically implausible estimates.

For the proposed system, we will first conduct a **k-fold calibration and validation followed by a full calibration** with ground truth C stock and GHG flux observations (3: Calibration / Validation). This is similar to the approach we used at Indigo Ag following the Climate Action Reserve Soil Enrichment Protocol. PEcAn has been used extensively for **hierarchical Bayesian calibration** against field measured pools and fluxes, as well as remotely-sensed data (Fer *et al.*, 2018, 2021; Dokoohaki *et al.*, 2021). After calibration, we will use the calibrated parameters to estimate C stock and GHG flux inventories (4: Calibrated Inventory). We will use statistical assimilation of C stocks to improve our estimates of the system states, including both C stocks as well as GHG fluxes to produce inventories (5: Assimilation) that will be updated annually as new drivers become available (6: Updates). These inventories will serve as the initial conditions for the forecast cycle. Similar to the ensemble weather forecasts, when making longer-term projections under different climate scenarios we can use downscaled multi-model (CMIP6) climate forecasts (Thrasher *et al.*, 2022; Gebrechorkos *et al.*, 2023) as drivers in this

forecast step. We will evaluate adoption of GHG mitigation practices and work with CARB staff to develop **ensembles of agricultural management scenarios** to generate scenario forecasts (7: Scenarios and Forecasts).

Overall, this system is the culmination of over a decade of cyberinfrastructure development, and represents the most complete and robust uncertainty accounting available for terrestrial ecosystem models, and provides a major advancement over other terrestrial data assimilation systems including CLM-DART (Fox *et al.*, 2022), CARDAMOM (Bloom *et al.*, 2016), and CCDAS (Castro-Morales *et al.*, 2019). Related work by Co-Is Dietze and Serbin has used a variety of data products to constrain the SIPNET model. These include GEDI AGB, a Landsat-based AGB estimate (Kennedy *et al.*, 2018), MODIS LAI (Knyazikhin *et al.*, 1998), SMAP soil moisture (Reichle *et al.*, 2019, 2021), and Ameriflux NEE and LE (Chu *et al.*, 2023). This suite of variables directly constrain major pools, including leaf C, stem C, soil C, soil moisture and land-atmosphere fluxes.

We will use **uncertainty analysis** to inform and prioritize our work. As described above, uncertainty will be partitioned into initial condition, driver (including meteorological, land use, and crop management), parameter, and process (model structural) error sources following our previous work (Dietze, 2017b; Raiho *et al.*, 2020). We have found that process uncertainty, followed by initial conditions and process error dominate predictability of forest C dynamics over multi-decadal time scales (Raiho *et al.*, 2020). We will perform an uncertainty analysis on this product to partition the impacts of observation error, model process error, model parameters, environmental drivers, and initial conditions on the joint uncertainties in C pools and GHG fluxes, and to assess the value of information of each data constraint to reduce these uncertainties. The results of these analyses will quantify the relative importance of different sources of uncertainty and allow us to estimate the uncertainty reduction expected from additional data sets or model improvements. We will report on limits of inventory and forecast uncertainty, and propose new data sets and their potential to reduce uncertainty.

Monitoring Data & Monitoring Workflow

The central concept of our monitoring plan is that a **lack of accurate management information is the key current limitation to large-scale agricultural modeling**. We will address this need by **extracting time-series information from field-scale satellite data** (Landsat and Sentinel), unlocking statewide **monitoring of tillage, precipitation, planting, harvest, and cover cropping**. Complementing these new management data, we will ensure spatially accurate model predictions by taking other model drivers from existing statewide data products to the greatest extent possible. Specifically, we will use existing satellite-derived data products that have a sustained track record of being open, available and continually updated. These include GPP (Jiang *et al.*, 2021) and LAI (Knyazikhin *et al.*, 1998) derived from NASA MODIS, OpenET evapotranspiration representing diverse sources and models (Melton *et al.*, 2022), NASA SMAP soil moisture (Reichle *et al.*, 2019, 2021), and USDA Cropland Data Layer for crop type (USDA NASS, 2024) (Table 1). Tillage and planting / harvest dates, including cover crop activity, will be

extracted from MODIS, VIIRS, Landsat and Sentinel timeseries building on a number of promising recent approaches (Thompson *et al.*, 2023). Irrigation will be inferred from the difference between reference and actual ET. Data that cannot yet be accurately inferred from satellite data, such as N management, will be inferred from crop type.

The new remotely-sensed data products being produced for this project (e.g., tillage, harvest, cover crops) will be based on state-of-the-art land cover algorithms, such as Landtrendr (Dara *et al.*, 2018; Zhu *et al.*, 2019) and CCDC (Zhu and Woodcock, 2014), that leverage the time-series nature of remotely-sensed data, rather than traditional static classification algorithms. We will classify cover crops using a winter greenness approach similar to Thompson *et al.* (2023) and Ahmed *et al.* (2023), tillage and planting/harvest via within-year time series (Azzari *et al.*, 2019; Zhang *et al.*, 2021; Deines *et al.*, 2023). These methods have all been previously used with success on a variety of crop systems and appear tractable for large-scale mapping across CA's diverse specialty crop regions, but we are not aware of any existing data product that provides a pre-calculated version.

In addition to allowing us to account for management changes in wall-to-wall modeling, this approach is well suited to data assimilation as described at the beginning of the Methods section. For example, monitoring estimates of SOC stock change can be improved by constraining the initial SOC stock at a given location. We will take stock estimates from model spin up using soil properties from SSURGO and land-use histories extracted from LandSat, then refine these through data assimilation of SOC estimates from soilGrids (Li *et al.*, no date).

Table 1: Data values to be monitored, with sources and purpose of monitoring

value	source	Spatial scale	Temporal scale	purpose
Historical through present weather	ERA5 (Hersbach <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	0.25°	hourly	Model driver, with ensemble based uncertainty, Stratified grid sampling
Weather through 2100	Downscaled CMIP6 (Thrasher <i>et al.</i> , 2022; Gebrechorkos <i>et al.</i> , 2023)	0.25°	daily	Model driver for future scenarios
Soil hydrological parameters	gSSURGO (Ramcharan <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Soil Survey	30 m	invariant	Model initial conditions, Stratified grid sampling

	Staff, 2023)			
Soil baseline SOC	SoilGrids (Poggio <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	250 m	invariant	Model initial conditions, stratified grid sampling
Crop identity	Cropland Data Layer (USDA NASS, 2024)	30 m	annual	Model initial conditions, Stratified grid sampling
GPP	(Jiang <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	250 m	daily	Constrains plant growth
LAI	MODIS (Knyazikhin <i>et al.</i> , 1998)	500 m	4 day	Constrains plant growth + biomass
evapotranspiration	openET (Melton <i>et al.</i> , 2022)	30 m	daily	Irrigation monitoring
Soil moisture	SMAP (Reichle <i>et al.</i> , 2019, 2021)	9 km	daily	Constrains GHG production + irrigation monitoring

Table 2: Managements used as input to the biogeochemistry model, and how they will be inferred by monitoring algorithms.

category	source	Spatial scale	Temporal scale	Notes
Crop identity	CDL (USDA NASS, 2024)	30 m	annual	Crops with similar physiology and management will be combined for modeling purposes
Planting and harvest	New for this project: computed from GPP+LAI	30 m	monthly	Temporal resolution is limited by clear-day overpass frequency
Tillage	New for this project: Computed from Landsat+Sentinel	30 m	monthly	Temporal resolution is limited by clear-day overpass frequency
Irrigation	New for this project: Computed from ET + soil water status	?	daily	Combines products a several spatial resolutions; effective

				scale TBD
Cover cropping	New for this project: Computed from Landsat+ Sentinel	30 m	monthly	Temporal resolution is limited by clear-day overpass frequency
Historic land use	New for this project: Computed from Landsat + Sentinel	30 m	yearly	Constrains SOC stock and biomass
Nutrient management	New for this project: estimated from crop identity, NASS county level records and crop-based guidelines and historic use.	30 m	yearly	No viable remote-sensed data available

Modeling Framework

Simplified Biogeochemistry Model

To simulate plant and soil C as well as the emissions of greenhouse gasses CH₄ and N₂O, we will build a **simplified biogeochemistry model** using SIPNET (Braswell *et al.*, 2005; Zobitz *et al.*, 2008) as a foundation and adding simplified biogeochemical dynamics based on DayCent. SIPNET has three vegetative carbon pools (leaf, stem, and root), a flexible number (1-3) of soil carbon pools, and a simple hydrological model. SIPNET is already being used for ecological forecasting and carbon cycle data assimilation within the PEcAn modeling framework with many of the same datasets that this project will use (Fer *et al.*, 2018; Dokoohaki *et al.*, 2021).

We chose SIPNET because it is a simplified biogeochemistry model that represents the processes of interest for the RFP. It is just complex enough to predict C stocks in plant biomass and soil, and modular enough that we can integrate the **new components required to simulate methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) GHG fluxes** in California’s cropland ecosystems. SIPNET predicts plant growth and senescence as well as soil carbon and water balance that controls both plant growth and production of these greenhouse gasses. SIPNET was explicitly designed to efficiently simulate carbon and water balance of ecosystems and be calibrated using daily flux measurements. SIPNET has a modular design that allows the complexity of the model to be adjusted through the settings file. This allows quantification of changes in model skill as additional biogeochemical processes are added (Zobitz *et al.*, 2008). We will keep with this design philosophy and start by adding what we consider the minimum additional components required to simulate the production of CH₄ and N₂O, starting with the pools and fluxes described in Figure 2.

We considered more complex crop models and found a few with the agronomic and biogeochemical components required for C stock and GHG flux accounting and prediction. These models include DNDC, DayCent, ecosys, DSSAT, and CLM. All of these models are orders of magnitude more complex and computationally intensive than SIPNET. Only DSSAT, ecosys, and CLM have open source licenses. We decided that the level of complexity of these models would not be justified by the time that would be required to set up and run them. At the same time, the PEcAn modeling workflow supports over 20 ecosystem models, including versions of CLM and DNDC, so future work could replace SIPNET with these or other models.

SIPNET's simplicity makes it tractable, computationally efficient, easier to learn, use, verify, and extend. Furthermore, SIPNET has a reduced data burden - for example, most agricultural models require lots of detailed and often long histories of management information. Fewer parameters are identifiable and justifiable than hundreds of manually tuned parameters found in more complex crop and ecosystem models. The computational efficiency of SIPNET makes the model amenable to the large number of runs required to run the model using probabilistic methods at high resolution at the state scale.

Following the SIPNET "simple" design philosophy, we will add simplified modules to simulate CH₄ and nitrous oxide N₂O production. Both of these GHG fluxes will require an estimate of the fraction of the soil that is anaerobic. Methanogenesis will be a function of substrate, aerobic soil fraction, and temperature. Because SIPNET does not already simulate nitrogen cycle dynamics, adding the minimum number of processes required to simulate N₂O emissions will be more complex. We will start by adding C:N ratios for each carbon pool. Using these C:N ratios, N mineralization will be proportional to C turnover through decomposition; analogously, plant N uptake will be proportional to plant growth. Fertilization and N fixation will add additional fluxes of N to the system. Like methanogenesis, nitrification and denitrification will be controlled by the availability of oxygen in the soil, which will be modeled as a function of soil moisture, as well as temperature and substrate. After implementing these dynamics required to simulate CH₄ and N₂O emissions, we may consider increasing the complexity of these components guided by biogeochemical theory (Schlesinger and Bernhardt, 2013) and implementation of approaches informed by other models including DayCent and DNDC (Cheng *et al.*, 2013; Tang *et al.*, 2024). Model complexity will only be increased if warranted by available data and expected uncertainty reduction.

Figure 2. Overview of SIPNET model components including existing carbon and hydrological cycle as well as proposed additions including a new N cycle required to simulate production of CH₄ and N₂O. Dashed lines represent key fluxes including photosynthesis and allocation (green), respiration of CO₂ (red), CH₄ (purple), and N₂O (gold) emissions. Existing SIPNET cycling components adapted from (Braswell *et al.*, 2005; Zobitz *et al.*, 2008); methanogenesis and nitrogen cycling from (Schlesinger and Bernhardt, 2013).

Model Calibration and Validation

We will calibrate and validate the model using a Bayesian approach already built in to PECAn, allowing us to leverage existing capabilities for sensitivity and uncertainty analysis, calibration, state data assimilation, and working with existing datasets.

As a first step, we will estimate parameter, initial condition, and input uncertainty. Most of the SIPNET parameters already have priors available in the PEcAn database, frequently with data to support further constraint using meta-analysis. As we build out the model, we will apply the same approaches to the estimation of prior parameter values following LeBauer et al (2013). A particular focus will be to estimate trait-based priors on the C:N ratio of plant and soil ecosystem organic matter stocks, as well as the reaction rates (K) for each flux. As discussed above, we regularly use ensemble based meteorological re-analyses and climate forecasts. And we will use soil data products uncertainty represented as either intervals or ensembles.

At each round of the Analysis/Forecast cycle, we will use PEcAn's automated sensitivity analysis and variance decomposition to partition uncertainties and use this information to inform the selection of parameters for calibration (LeBauer *et al.*, 2013) and assimilation.

Once we have set up and evaluated the initial runs, we will choose the most appropriate calibration algorithm. We will briefly review approaches already supported by PEcAn. For a simple model like SIPNET, we typically leverage the BayesianTools package (Hartig, Minunno and Paul, 2023) that implements a large number of Bayesian MCMC algorithms including Metropolis, Differential Evolution, DREAM, and T-walk as well as Sequential Monte Carlo (SMC) approaches. The second approach, which is designed for computationally-intensive calibration problems including slow models, large data, or large numbers of sites (Fer *et al.*, 2018). This approach relies on model emulation. Specifically, we evaluate the model across a number of design points in multivariate parameter space (in parallel), compute statistics of model performance (e.g. RMSE), and then use Gaussian Process models to build multivariate response surfaces that predict error as a function of parameter value. We can then use this emulator within a traditional MCMC. As one example, this approach was able to reduce the time required to calibrate the ED2 model from an estimated 84 years via brute-force MCMC to a few hours via model emulation. The emulator-based approach has also been extended to a hierarchical version that is able to capture the spatial variability in a model's optimal parameters, which is needed to capture the often unexplained heterogeneity in environmental processes (Fer *et al.*, 2021).

For this project, we will construct a **joint likelihood that accounts for the information content in each data source**. This is a challenging step, but we will start with PEcAn's current default options that include a standard Gaussian likelihood, a linear-bias corrected Gaussian likelihood, and an asymmetric heteroskedastic Laplacian, with the last developed specifically to support eddy-covariance data.

To maximize the ratio of information content to computational effort, our current system does not run on a rectangular grid, but rather uses an irregular network that allows us to oversample where there are steep environmental gradients (e.g., coastlines and mountains) and spread out points where systems are more homogenous (e.g., valley cropland). The use of an irregular grid also allows us to **anchor** our calibration and validation to sites of where data is available. This use of anchor sites also avoids issues of scale mismatch that are common in large-scale model

runs, where the outputs for a coarse gridcell are not always directly comparable to the observations at locations (e.g., flux towers) within those grid cells.

After selecting anchor sites we will add additional point locations selected in a stratified random manner, using a k-means clustering to account for differences in climate, soils, topography, land use / land cover (including crop type), and time since last land use change and / or conversion to cropland. This stratified random sampling will also preferentially select points with available data for calibration and validation. The overall point density selected will be no less than one point per 25km², with additional points in locations with steep topographic gradients or multiple crop types of crop 0.1 degrees.

Once site selection is completed, we will use existing automated PEcAn workflows to download and prep the data needed for model inputs (e.g., meteorology, soil physical properties), initial conditions, and data assimilation constraints. Initial test runs will leverage a subset of anchor sites, and then be scaled up to production runs.

During model development, we will continuously test the model against cropland sites in the Ameriflux network. Sipnet was designed specifically to be parameterized from eddy covariance sites, and has been widely tested across a wide range of ecosystems in previous work. By using well-characterized sites as the model development testbed we will ensure that the GHG-enabled model preserves its performance under conditions where it was previously validated, and will avoid overfitting the final model to the observations that can provide independent validation or final calibration model. Note that while PNET, which served as the initial basis for SIPNET's design, was originally developed for forest ecosystems, SIPNET is already used operationally for a wide-variety of non-forest systems in the CMS carbon monitoring system (crop, grassland, shrubland, etc.) and all processes it represents (photosynthesis, allocation, respiration, turnover, etc.) work similarly in forests and croplands, so this approach does not risk compromising its ultimate performance on croplands.

The highest-value data for validation of a cropland model are published observations from controlled experiments that compare alternative crop management against a business-as-usual control, and which ideally report measurements of crop root and shoot biomass, GHG flux, and SOC stock across many years. Not many experiments meet all these criteria at once, but many more provide useful measurements of at least one variable. At sites with multiple variables observed, our multivariate likelihood will gain information about the correlations between variables and propagate those to a correct uncertainty about sites with fewer variables. To identify validation data, we will select published experiments from existing databases. For SOC these will include AgEvidence (Atwood and Wood, 2020), the systematic review of (Haddaway *et al.*, 2017), and the cropland sites in SoDAH (Wieder *et al.*, 2021). Ameriflux sites providing GHG flux measurements in croplands available for reuse (CC-BY) include at least 25 measuring CH₄ (17 rice) and 14 measuring N₂O. We will also gather N₂O measurements from GRACenet (Del Grosso *et al.*, 2013) and the CA farmland emissions of (Verhoeven *et al.*, 2017). To ensure that the validation demonstrates model performance under California

conditions, We will use data from California and from sites that are biophysically comparable with respect to climate, soil types, and managements.

The simplicity of our model provides an advantage for validation. Existing biogeochemical models with complex site-specific parameterization requirements are often limited by unavailability of detailed management data from sites that could otherwise be used for validation (Mathers *et al.*, 2023). Since the proposed model is designed to be driven from simple remotely-sensed inputs, the publications used for our validation need not report management in detail. Small-lot trials that cannot be resolved as Landsat pixels will still need the publication to report basic data such as tillage, planting, and cover crop management, but will not require site level soil characterization or crop phenology. Additionally, the modeling system is designed to facilitate addition of new data sources as they become available, so this validation can be readily extended in the future as new datasets come online.

To demonstrate model performance across the range of available data while avoiding overfitting, we will use the cross-validation approach (Mathers *et al.*, 2023) and previously implemented by Black and LeBauer following the Climate Action Reserve's Soil Enrichment Protocol. This approach quantifies model bias and verifies that model uncertainty is commensurate with the uncertainty of the observations. In addition to the threshold-based (adequate/inadequate) evaluation (Mathers *et al.*, 2023) we will calculate a continuous ranked probability score (CRPS). CRPS is a widely-used metric for validating probabilistic models, as it accounts for both model accuracy (residual error, model bias) and model precision (width of the predictive distribution), penalizing models for either being imprecise (intervals too wide) or falsely overconfident (intervals too narrow). We expect the use of cross-validation to be especially important for validating CH₄ flux, because the number of observations available is small and cross-validation allows each available datapoint to inform both the calibration and validation processes.

C Stock and GHG Flux Inventories and Forecasts

When delivered, the measurement and modeling system will generate comprehensive C stock and GHG flux estimates for California cropland, both as annual inventories and scenario-based forecasts. The system that we provide and train CARB staff on will have the capacity to generate annually updated **inventories** as well as **scenario based forecasts**. These products will include uncertainties represented both statistically and as ensemble-based uncertainties.

Following cross-validation, we will perform a joint calibration of model parameters across the data C stock and GHG flux data that we have collected. We will then use state data assimilation of the SoilGrids soil C layer to directly constrain soil C stocks and indirectly constrain other model C pools and GHG fluxes. This will represent the first inventory product. If time permits, the state data assimilation will also include the other data constraints that Dietze and Serbin are currently using in their NASA CMS product, as a means of directly constraining the other modeled C and water pools, including but not limited to: MODIS LAI, SMAP soil moisture, and GEDI biomass. Next, these constrained soil C stocks, including uncertainties, will be used as

initial conditions for forecasts that predict future inventories under different scenarios of climate change, land use change, and adoption of agronomic practices.

Uncertainty will be represented in data products using **ensemble-based uncertainty accounting**, as recommended by the NASA Carbon Monitoring System Uncertainty Working Group (Kennedy R, Serbin S, CMS Uncertainty working group., 2024). This approach is the simplest and most flexible approach to spatiotemporal uncertainty propagation, and most straightforward to use down-stream analyses. In this approach, each ensemble member is treated as a random sample from the posterior distribution of the model prediction. Downstream statistical and simulation analyses can be directly performed on these ensemble members. For example, the county mean of C stocks and GHG emissions can be calculated for each ensemble member separately, and then the across-ensemble variance would provide an estimate of county level uncertainty. The advantage of this approach over the more naive approach of calculating uncertainty at each pixel is that this approach retains the spatial and temporal correlations of uncertainties to be handled in a way that is most appropriate for the downstream analysis, whether that be aggregation or further propagation. Following the Ecological Forecasting Initiative's open-source community standard (Dietze *et al.*, 2023), gridded data products will include layers for means, uncertainties, and ensemble members. The county level summaries will be provided with means, quantiles, and uncertainties.

We will perform additional, iterative validation against new 'ground truth' data as they become available. For example, we will compare inventories to measurements of C stocks (SOC, biomass) and GHG fluxes (N₂O and CH₄) as new data that were not available at the time of calibration and validation become available. We will work with CARB staff to determine the scope of these efforts.

In order to increase confidence and identify discrepancies, we will compare the inventories that we produce to other estimates that have been derived using different methods. This will be an intercomparison of derived products rather than a validation. There are numerous estimates of crop biomass. For example, a previous CARB / NASA project produced maps of California perennial crop C stock inventories (Ross *et al.*, 2022). Multiple datasets provide GHG flux estimates using diverse approaches. These include global gridded agricultural GHG fluxes from empirical models of N₂O and CH₄ including IPCC default equations (Takele, 2021). There are also maps of N₂O flux upscaled from ground based measurements (Wang *et al.*, 2020) and inverted from atmospheric transport models (Thompson, Patra and Wilson, 2019). For CH₄ multiple satellite derived open datasets will be available (Jacob *et al.*, 2022).

Data and Documentation

Our project is committed to fulfilling **CARB's open-source, reuseability, and documentation standards**. Our team, with a strong background in **open science**, will ensure data, software, and documentation adhere to these principles. While remaining committed to CARBs

confidentiality policy, we are willing to continue our open science approaches that include developing software in public repositories and providing access to early versions of data products with CARB approval.

Software

Open Source Licensing: All software will be available under BSD 3-Clause, MIT, or compatible open source license.

PEcAn is integral to the project and is fully open-source and well documented. PEcAn's PostGIS database (LeBauer *et al.*, 2018) provides comprehensive tracking of provenance including inputs, outputs, parameters, model runs, and model benchmarking.

Changes to the **SIPNET** model will be developed and released with a permissive open source license. The PEcAn Project has already worked with the SIPNET model developers to move the code to a public space on GitHub (<https://github.com/pecanproject/sipnet>) under the BSD 3-Clause license. All changes made as part of this proposal will be contributed back to the SIPNET repository.

Over the past 20 years, Kooper's team at the National Center for Supercomputing Applications (NCSA) has been working on open source projects to support scientific computing. This project will leverage the extensive knowledge and diverse computing environments at NCSA to engineer a pipeline that will seamlessly transfer to CARB computing infrastructure at the end of the project. Kooper's experience includes not only developing, documenting, and testing code, but also setting up pipelines that will do continuous integration tests and continuous deployment. For continuous deployment we will deploy the code in a cluster and have it available for testing within minutes after the code has passed the integration tests. This will allow the developers to see their changes as they will be on the final system.

We have found this step to be critical to make sure that we can do full scale system tests that will show us any issues with the performance as we move to full size tests. This is especially important to make sure we meet the goals to run the system at large scale. We want this test system to be as close as possible to the final system, to see the time and resources needed to do a full scale run.

At NCSA we will leverage technologies including OpenStack, Docker, and Kubernetes to have a persistent system where the data and analysis infrastructure will be available continuously in development, testing, and production environments. The most computationally intensive part of the workflow is running the model, and these can be scaled up using kubernetes or HPC cluster computing resources. We will leverage of our existing experience with deployments such as Docker, Helm, and Aptainer to facilitate deployment to CARB or other computing infrastructure.

During the first three months (Task 1 Conceptual Framework) we will work closely with CARB staff to ensure that the technologies used are best suited for computing resources available to

CARB. Through NCSA we have access to diverse computing resources including OpenStack and HPCs and this will allow us to adjust our deployment framework according to CARB's needs to enable seamless transfer of technology and knowledge.

Data products

Outputs of both modeling and monitoring pipelines will be stored as CSV (county level) and netCDF (gridded) files using the Ecological Forecasting Initiative's open community standard (Dietze et al 2023). We will also work with CARB to develop data products in preferred formats and develop protocols for the approval and dissemination of data products.

Inventories, scenario based forecasts, and monitoring of agronomic management practices will be generated as both gridded and estimates at the state and county, in aggregate and by crop functional type. To facilitate interoperability with the broader crop modeling community, management events will use Agricultural Model Intercomparison Project's ICASA vocabulary (White *et al.*, 2013) in a simple JSON structure that has been adopted for use with PEcAn by the Finnish Meteorological Society's carbon monitoring program (Nevalainen *et al.*, 2022).

PEcAn's database tracks workflow provenance, including inputs, outputs and model runs, and this information can be provided as meta-data alongside data products.

Documentation and Publications

Documentation, reports, training materials, and publications will be created and published under permissive copyright and in accordance with CARB's provisions on ownership of work, copyrightable materials, and confidentiality

All publications will be submitted to journals that are either fully open-access or provide an option to opt-in to open-access for an additional fee. All code used to perform post hoc analyses will be open-source, either in the PEcAn Github repository or in stand-alone repositories documenting individual papers. To the extent possible, papers and reports will be developed as automated reproducible workflows leveraging tools like R Markdown to embed analyses, figures, and tables in the paper itself. All derived data sets will be publicly archived and placed into the public domain (CC-0) when possible or released with a permissive copyright (CC-BY).

Work Plan and Work Schedule

Work Plan

The management plan (above) describes project operational protocols, including supervision, oversight, workload distribution, and ensuring that the project will remain on schedule. We

provide in Figure 3 an overview of the project timeline, leader, and number of hours required for each task, and describe each task in more detail in the work schedule.

Task and subtask leads are identified by initials (CB: Black, DL: LeBauer, MD: Dietze, ML: Longfritz, RK: Kooper).

Figure 3: Summary of the project timeline, showing the person responsible, hours required, and active periods for each task.

Work Schedule

	Deliverable title, subtasks, lead initials and hours allocated	Deliverable Description	Due Date
Task 1 (MD)	Conceptual Framework Development		
1.1 (MD)	Draft conceptual framework -Define new functionality to be added to SIPNET. ML, 8 -Define architecture and features required for operational pipeline using PEcAn. DL, 16 -Define new monitoring and inventory data products. CB, 16 -Define infrastructure for	Provide a draft report describing the overall concept that will result in the California Cropland Monitoring and modeling framework. Include flow diagrams, data needs, scientific justification, and specifics for newly created data.	2 months from start

	development and testing. RK, 16 - (milestone) Write draft report and submit for review by CARB. MD, 36		
1.2 (MD)	Final conceptual framework -(milestone) Revise draft based on feedback for scope, clarity, and scientific validity. Finalize document and submit. MD, 24	Provide a final report describing the overall concept that will result in the California Cropland Monitoring and modeling framework. Include flow diagrams, data needs, scientific justification, and specifics for newly created data. This report will be responsive to CARB feedback from Task 1.1 and be sufficient as justification for the approach taken for the remainder of the project.	3 months from start

	Deliverable title, subtasks, lead initials and hours allocated	Deliverable Description	Due Date
Task 2 (DL)	Modeling Framework		
2.1 (DL)	Draft modeling framework -Design modeling information flow. DL, 8 -Specify structure and implementation tools of simplified biogeochemistry model for California croplands, including equations to be used and required inputs, outputs, parameters and states. DL, 16 -Identify data sources to be used as model initial conditions, drivers, and targets of calibration / assimilation. CB, 16 -Define approach to parameterization, calibration, uncertainty analysis, data assimilation, and data product generation steps. DL, 16 -Identify PEcAn workflow	Provide a draft report describing the modeling processing workflow, including the inputs, processes, and outputs. This draft report should go into detail as to how calculations will be performed, the language in which the model will be written, any temporal and spatial considerations that will be included, and the spatial temporal resolution that will be used. A method for testing accuracy shall also be proposed for both inventory and future projection uses.	5 months from start

	<p>components that will be used and additional required project-specific work. DL, 8</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Identify infrastructure needs for model execution at state scale. RK, 24 -(milestone) Write Draft Modeling Framework and submit to CARB for review. DL, 36 		
2.2 (DL)	<p>Final modeling framework</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -(milestone) Refine draft based on feedback, finalize document and submit. DL, 24 	<p>Provide a final report describing the modeling project. This report will be responsive to CARB feedback from Task 2.1 and be sufficient as justification for the approach taken for the remainder of the project.</p>	6 months
2.3 (ML)	<p>Task 2 Progress Report 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Implement first draft of model GHG extensions. ML, 240 -Write tests for SIPNET functionality. ML, 32 -Document model implementation including 'quick start' instructions for initial evaluation. ML, 32 -Prepare datasets to be used for model initial conditions and drivers. ML, 32 -Initial deployment of infrastructure, to be used when preparing datasets and initial setup for models. RK, 48 -(milestone) Write progress report 1. ML, 24 	<p>Provide a report or presentation demonstrating the progress creating this model to this point. The Contractor will work with CARB staff to identify the appropriate amount of information.</p>	12 months
2.4 (DL)	<p>Task 2 Progress Report 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Assemble and estimate uncertainty in initial conditions, drivers, and prior parameterizations required to run SIPNET. DL, 120 -Extend, test, and harden SIPNET PEcAn couplers. DL, 80 -Deploy development infrastructure for PEcAn and automate core PEcAn + SIPNET pipeline. RK, 120 	<p>Provide a report or presentation demonstrating the progress creating this model to this point. The Contractor will work with CARB staff to identify the appropriate amount of information.</p>	16 months

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Perform model uncertainty analysis. DL, 100 -(milestone) Write progress report 2 that demonstrates initial small scale runs and uncertainty analysis of model. DL, 36 		
2.5 (CB)	<p>Task 2 Progress Report 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Assemble C stock and GHG calibration, validation and assimilation datasets; estimate associated uncertainties. CB, 260 -Implement and test multi-objective likelihood. CB, 260 -Run k-fold model calibration and validation. CB, 120 -Test and integrate models into development system, as well as orchestrate tests. RK, 36 -(milestone) Write progress report 3. CB, 36 	<p>Provide a report or presentation demonstrating the progress creating this model to this point. The Contractor will work with CARB staff to identify the appropriate amount of information.</p>	20 months
2.6 (DL)	<p>Inventory demonstration and tutorial</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Generate gridded ensemble of C stock and GHG fluxes for California cropland agriculture. DL, 200 -Generate county and state level aggregated C stock and GHG fluxes as ensemble samples and summary statistics. DL, 120 -Assimilate soil C stock estimates to reduce uncertainties in C stocks and GHG emissions. MD, 320 -Package all workflow system components into a stack that can be deployed on standard high performance computing and cloud infrastructure. RK, 56 -Document and create training materials including reproducible and extensible workflows demonstrating how to configure and simulate annual C stock and GHG inventories. CB, 72 -(milestone) Provide training in 	<p>The Contractor will demonstrate the use of this model for inventory purposes. This includes estimating the past and current carbon stocks and GHG statewide and on a county level. General accuracy assessments shall be included. The Contractor will provide a tutorial for running and manipulating the codes, workflows, and modeling pipelines to ensure that State staff will have the ability to replicate the deliverables given that State staff have the skills to perform big data compute tasks. The Contractor will ensure that all workflows compile, run, and execute tasks correctly and will work with State staff to adjust the computer codes to ensure that workflows can be reproduced using the computational resources available to State</p>	23 months

	<p>calculation of annual C stock and GHG inventories. CB, 40 -(milestone) Confirm that code can be run by CARB staff on CARB computing resources. RK, 24</p>	<p>staff.</p>	
<p>2.7 (CB)</p>	<p>Future projection modeling demonstration and hand-off</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Generate gridded ensemble of C stock and GHG fluxes for California cropland agriculture under future climate change. DL, 80 -Simulate multiple future C stock and GHG flux inventories under alternative scenarios. CB, 80 -Document and create training materials including reproducible and extensible workflows demonstrating how to configure and simulate alternate future scenarios. CB, 48 -(milestone) Provide training in future projection modeling and scenario evaluation. CB, 40 	<p>The Contractor will demonstrate the use of this model for future projection modeling on the scenarios outlined in this task, and how alternative scenarios can be generated in the future by CARB staff. The code shall be in a clean and understandable form with documentation and comments. All scripts needed to compile and run the process chain will also be provided. The Contractor will ensure that CARB staff can run the model for both inventory and future projection purposes. The scripts needed to develop alternative management scenarios will also be provided.</p>	<p>27 months</p>

	Deliverable title, subtasks, lead initials and hours allocated	Deliverable Description	Due Date (months from start)
<p>Task 3 (MD)</p>	<p>Monitoring Framework</p>		
<p>3.1 (MD)</p>	<p>Draft monitoring framework</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Catalog available datasets and algorithms. CB, 24 -Design implementation of a suite of algorithms for estimating agronomic management and land use change events. MD, 80 -Design analysis pipeline for generation of new data products. MD, 80 -Identify infrastructure needs for monitoring at state scale. RK, 16 	<p>Provide a draft report describing the modeling process, including the inputs, processes, and outputs. This draft report should go into detail as to how calculations will be performed, spatial and temporal resolution, the sensors and any other data that will be used, and the validation procedure that is proposed.</p>	<p>7 months</p>

	<p>-(milestone) Write draft monitoring report and submit to CARB for review. CB, 36</p>		
3.2 (MD)	<p>Final monitoring framework</p> <p>-(milestone) Refine draft based on feedback, finalize document and submit. MD, 36</p>	<p>Provide a final report describing the modeling project. This report will be responsive to CARB feedback from Task 3.1 and be sufficient as justification for the approach taken for the remainder of the project.</p>	8 months
3.3 (MD)	<p>Task 3 Progress Report 1</p> <p>-Implement algorithm to detect planting, harvest, cover cropping, and biomass removal. MD, 240</p> <p>-Implement algorithm to detect changes in cropland use. MD, 160</p> <p>-Assemble vegetation management validation data. CB, 40</p> <p>-Conduct validation and estimate uncertainty. CB, 72</p> <p>-(milestone) Write and submit progress report to CARB. MD, 36</p>	<p>Provide a report or presentation demonstrating the progress creating this model to this point. The Contractor will work with CARB staff to identify the appropriate amount of information.</p>	12 months
3.4 (MD)	<p>Task 3 Progress Report 2</p> <p>-Implement algorithm to detect tillage events. MD, 120</p> <p>-Implement algorithm to detect irrigation events. MD, 120</p> <p>-Assemble tillage and irrigation validation data. CB, 34</p> <p>-Validate data products and estimate uncertainty. CB, 48</p> <p>-Generate gridded maps of agronomic management events, including uncertainty, for use in modeling framework. MD, 40</p> <p>-(milestone) Write and submit progress report to CARB. CB, 36</p>	<p>Provide a report or presentation demonstrating the progress creating this model to this point. The Contractor will work with CARB staff to identify the appropriate amount of information.</p>	16 months
3.5 (MD)	<p>Task 3 Progress Report 3</p> <p>-Prioritize next steps based on</p>	<p>Provide a report or presentation demonstrating the progress creating this model to this point.</p>	20 months

	<p>uncertainty analyses from modeling pipeline. MD, 24</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Improve algorithms and / or add data products to reduce uncertainty. MD, 116 -Validate data products and estimate uncertainty. MD, 48 -Generate updated maps of monitored events. MD, 24 -(milestone) Write and submit progress report to CARB. MD, 36 	<p>The Contractor will work with CARB staff to identify the appropriate amount of information.</p>	
3.6 (MD)	<p>Final product demonstration, tutorial, and data hand off</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Document and create training materials including reproducible and extensible workflows demonstrating how to run entire workflow for generation of cropland monitoring data. MD, 120 -(milestone) Provide training in generation of cropland monitoring data products. CB, 64 	<p>The Contractor will demonstrate the final products for as long a time period that is possible along with an accuracy assessment. All data developed through this project and everything in the required form needed to run the model from Task 1 will be provided to CARB with appropriate meta-data. The Contractor will provide a tutorial for running and manipulating the codes, workflows, and processing workflows that generated this data to ensure that State staff will have the ability to replicate the deliverables given that State staff have the skills to perform big data compute tasks. The Contractor will ensure that all workflows compile, run, and execute tasks correctly and will work with State staff to adjust the computer codes to ensure that workflows can be reproduced using the computational resources available to State staff.</p>	24 months
3.7 (CB)	<p>Final report and code hand-off</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -(milestone) Write and submit final report on cropland monitoring. CB, 84 -(milestone) Confirm that code can 	<p>The Contractor will provide a final report of the final products that include the process that produced these products, a scientific basis for the approached used, an accuracy</p>	27 months

	<p>be run by CARB staff on CARB computing resources. RK, 40</p>	<p>assessment, and any insight that are revealed from this data itself. The code shall be in a clean and understandable form with documentation and comments. All scripts needed to compile and run the process chain will also be provided. The Contractor will ensure that CARB staff can run the process to produce this data into the future updated through time.</p>	
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	Deliverable title, subtasks, lead initials and hours allocated	Deliverable Description	Due Date
Task 4 (CB)	Communication of Scientific Results		
4.1 (CB)	Weekly meetings	CARB reserves the right to request weekly one (1) hour catchup meetings. This could be reduced in frequency at CARB staff's discretion.	Weekly
4.2 (ML + DL)	<p>Present at AGU 2025</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Present SIPNET + GHG model. ML, 24 -Present Data and Model Uncertainty Analysis. DL, 24 	<p>Contractor will present this work at the American Geophysical Union annual meetings in 2025 and 2026. The Contractor will notify CARB of where the presentation will occur and will provide a copy of the presentation at least two (2) weeks before the presentation for internal review. The Contractor will address any comments/considerations given by CARB staff. CARB will be credited as a funding source in the presentation.</p>	December 2025
4.3 (MD + CB + DL)	<p>Present at AGU 2026</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Present monitoring algorithms and data products. MD, 24 -Present Soil C & GHG inventories. CB, 24 -Present on Uncertainty analysis and propagation. DL, 24 	<p>Contractor will address any comments/considerations given by CARB staff. CARB will be credited as a funding source in the presentation.</p>	December 2026
4.4 (CB)	<p>Draft Final Report</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -(milestone) Write draft report and submit for review by CARB. CB, 72 	<p>Provide a final report describing the entire project. This report shall build off and include existing reports and a</p>	1.5 months before end of

		propagated uncertainty values for the carbon stocks and GHG fluxes that include the aggregated uncertainty through the entire process pipeline. The final results and uncertainty will include all components of the entire monitoring and modeling framework. This report will also include an assessment of how and why carbon stocks and GHG fluxes have changed through time throughout the entire time period that could be assessed (past, present, and future), and any scientific inferences that can be drawn from this project. Also include recommendations for any further enhancements that could occur with additional funding.	contract
4.5 (CB)	Final Report -(milestone) Refine draft based on feedback, finalize document and submit. CB, 48	This will be the final report form of Task 4.4. This final report will be responsive to CARB staff comments from the draft. This report will also be ADA compliant sufficient for public consumption on State websites.	0.5 months before end of contract
4.6 (DL)	Publish paper on new Sipnet model -Revise Task 2.3-2.5 documentation into paper on SIPNET + GHG emissions. DL, 96		Ongoing
4.7 (MD)	Publish paper monitoring workflow -Revise Task 3.3-3.6 documentation into paper on monitoring workflows. MD, 80		Ongoing
4.8 (CB)	Publish data paper -Revise data documentation into data paper. CB, 64 -Archive data products in appropriate data repository. CB, 16		Ongoing

Conflict of Interest and Confidentiality Statement

Please see Attachment 12 for signed statements from all staff.

Subcontracts / Subcontractors

Pools and Fluxes LLC, operated by Black, will be the prime contractor for this project. Dietze (23%), Kooper (8%), LeBauer (31%), and Longfritz (7%) will each be subcontractors. See the Personnel and Experience section for descriptions of each and the work to be completed by them, and Attachment 9 for contact details.

Cost Detail

Please see the Cost Proposal, attached immediately following this Technical Proposal and separately page-numbered.

References

Ahmed, Z. *et al.* (2023) 'Winter-time cover crop identification: A remote sensing-based methodological framework for new and rapid data generation', *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 125(103564), p. 103564. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2023.103564>.

Atwood, L.W. and Wood, S.A. (2020) 'AgEvidence US: Agro-environmental responses of conservation agricultural practices published from 1980 to 2020'. KNB Data Repository. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5063/F16Q1VQP>.

Azzari, G. *et al.* (2019) 'Satellite mapping of tillage practices in the North Central US region from 2005 to 2016', *Remote Sensing of the Environment*, 221, pp. 417–429. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2018.11.010>.

Black, C.K. *et al.* (2017) 'Elevated CO and temperature increase soil C losses from a soybean-maize ecosystem', *Global change biology*, 23(1), pp. 435–445. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13378>.

Bloom, A.A. *et al.* (2016) 'The decadal state of the terrestrial carbon cycle: Global retrievals of terrestrial carbon allocation, pools, and residence times', *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 113(5), pp. 1285–1290. Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1515160113>.

Braswell, B.H. *et al.* (2005) 'Estimating diurnal to annual ecosystem parameters by synthesis of a carbon flux model with eddy covariance net ecosystem exchange observations', *Global change biology*, 11(2), pp. 335–355. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2005.00897.x>.

Burnette, M. *et al.* (2018) 'TERRA-REF Data Processing Infrastructure', in *Proceedings of the Practice and Experience on Advanced Research Computing. PEARC '18: Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing*, New York, NY, USA: ACM. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3219104.3219152>.

Castro-Morales, K. *et al.* (2019) 'Three decades of simulated global terrestrial carbon fluxes from a data assimilation system confronted with different periods of observations', *Biogeosciences*, 16(15), pp. 3009–3032. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-16-3009-2019>.

Cheng, K. *et al.* (2013) 'Predicting methanogenesis from rice paddies using the DAYCENT ecosystem model', *Ecological modelling*, 261-262, pp. 19–31. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2013.04.003>.

Chu, H. *et al.* (2023) 'AmeriFlux BASE data pipeline to support network growth and data sharing', *Scientific data*, 10(1), p. 614. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02531-2>.

Cowdery, E. and Yeluripati, J. (2022) 'The RETINA Project: Dynamic monitoring, reporting and verification for implementing negative emission strategies in managed ecosystems'. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu22-12764>.

Dara, A. *et al.* (2018) 'Mapping the timing of cropland abandonment and recultivation in northern Kazakhstan using annual Landsat time series', *Remote sensing of environment*, 213, pp. 49–60. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2018.05.005>.

Davis, S.C., Abatzoglou, J.T. and LeBauer, D.S. (2021) 'Expanded Potential Growing Region and Yield Increase for *Agave americana* with Future Climate', *Agronomy*, 11(11), p. 2109. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy11112109>.

Deines, J.M. *et al.* (2023) 'Field-scale dynamics of planting dates in the US Corn Belt from 2000 to 2020', *Remote Sensing of the Environment*, 291(113551), p. 113551. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2023.113551>.

Del Grosso, S.J. *et al.* (2013) 'Introducing the GRACEnet/REAP Data Contribution, Discovery, and Retrieval System', *Journal of environmental quality*, 42(4), pp. 1274–1280. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2013.03.0097>.

Dietze, M.C. (2017a) *Ecological Forecasting*. Princeton University Press. Available at: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=M3ygDgAAQBAJ>.

Dietze, M.C. (2017b) 'Prediction in ecology: a first-principles framework', *Ecological applications: a publication of the Ecological Society of America*, 27(7), pp. 2048–2060. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.1589>.

Dietze, M.C. *et al.* (2023) 'A community convention for ecological forecasting: Output files and

metadata version 1.0', *Ecosphere*, 14(11). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecs2.4686>.

Dietze, M.C., Lebauer, D.S. and Kooper, R. (2013) 'On improving the communication between models and data', *Plant, cell & environment*, 36(9), pp. 1575–1585. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/pce.12043>.

Doerr, J. (2018) *Measure What Matters: How Google, Bono, and the Gates Foundation Rock the World with OKRs*. Penguin. Available at: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=u2NDDwAAQBAJ>.

Dokoohaki, H. *et al.* (2021) 'A novel model–data fusion approach to terrestrial carbon cycle reanalysis across the contiguous U.S using SIPNET and PEcAn state data assimilation system v. 1.7.2'. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-2021-236>.

Dokoohaki, H. *et al.* (2022) 'Development of an open-source regional data assimilation system in PEcAn v. 1.7.2: application to carbon cycle reanalysis across the contiguous US using SIPNET', *Geoscientific model development*, 15(8), pp. 3233–3252. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-15-3233-2022>.

Fer, I. *et al.* (2018) 'Linking big models to big data: efficient ecosystem model calibration through Bayesian model emulation', *Biogeosciences*, 15(19), pp. 5801–5830. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-15-5801-2018>.

Fer, I. *et al.* (2021) 'Capturing site-to-site variability through Hierarchical Bayesian calibration of a process-based dynamic vegetation model', *bioRxiv*. bioRxiv. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.04.28.441243>.

Fox, A.M. *et al.* (2018) 'Evaluation of a data assimilation system for land surface models using CLM4.5', *Journal of advances in modeling earth systems*, 10(10), pp. 2471–2494. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018ms001362>.

Fox, A.M. *et al.* (2022) 'Assimilation of global satellite leaf area estimates reduces modeled global carbon uptake and energy loss by terrestrial ecosystems', *Journal of geophysical research. Biogeosciences*, 127(8). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022jg006830>.

Gebrechorkos, S. *et al.* (2023) 'A high-resolution daily global dataset of statistically downscaled CMIP6 models for climate impact analyses', *Scientific data*, 10(1), p. 611. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02528-x>.

Haddaway, N.R. *et al.* (2017) 'How does tillage intensity affect soil organic carbon? A systematic review', *Environmental evidence*, 6(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13750-017-0108-9>.

Hartig, F., Minunno, F. and Paul, S. (2023) 'BayesianTools: General-Purpose MCMC and SMC Samplers and Tools for Bayesian Statistics'. Available at: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=BayesianTools>.

Hersbach, H. *et al.* (2020) 'The ERA5 global reanalysis', *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 146(730), pp. 1999–2049. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.3803>.

Jacob, D.J. *et al.* (2022) 'Quantifying methane emissions from the global scale down to point sources using satellite observations of atmospheric methane', *Atmospheric Chemistry and*

Physics, 22(14), pp. 9617–9646. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-22-9617-2022>.

Jaiswal, D. *et al.* (2017) 'Brazilian sugarcane ethanol as an expandable green alternative to crude oil use', *Nature climate change*, 7(11), pp. 788–792. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate3410>.

Jiang, C. *et al.* (2021) 'A daily, 250 m and real-time gross primary productivity product (2000–present) covering the contiguous United States', *Earth system science data*, 13(2), pp. 281–298. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-13-281-2021>.

Kalnay, E. (2003) *Atmospheric Modeling, Data Assimilation and Predictability*. Cambridge University Press. Available at: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=Uqc7zC7NULMC>.

Kennedy, R. *et al.* (2018) 'Implementation of the LandTrendr algorithm on Google earth engine', *Remote sensing*, 10(5), p. 691. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs10050691>.

Kennedy R, Serbin S, CMS Uncertainty working group. (2024) 'Characterizing and communicating uncertainty: lessons from NASA's Carbon Monitoring System', *Environmental Research Letters*, *in review* [Preprint].

Knyazikhin, Y. *et al.* (1998) 'Synergistic algorithm for estimating vegetation canopy leaf area index and fraction of absorbed photosynthetically active radiation from MODIS and MISR data', *Journal of geophysical research*, 103(D24), pp. 32257–32275. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1029/98jd02462>.

LeBauer, D. *et al.* (2018) 'BETYdb: a yield, trait, and ecosystem service database applied to second-generation bioenergy feedstock production', *Global change biology. Bioenergy*, 10(1), pp. 61–71. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcbb.12420>.

LeBauer, D. *et al.* (2023) 'Increasing racial diversity in the North American Plant Phenotyping Network through conference participation support', *The Plant Phenome Journal*, 6(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/ppj2.20075>.

LeBauer, D.S. *et al.* (2013) 'Facilitating feedbacks between field measurements and ecosystem models', *Ecological monographs*, 83(2), pp. 133–154. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1890/12-0137.1>.

Lewis, J.M., Lakshmivaran, S. and Dhall, S. (2006) *Dynamic Data Assimilation: A Least Squares Approach*. Cambridge University Press. Available at: https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=MkydCKWIm_QC.

Liljedahl, A.K. *et al.* (2019) 'Permafrost Discovery Gateway: A web platform to enable discovery and knowledge-generation of permafrost Big Imagery products', in. *AGU Fall Meeting 2019*, San Francisco, USA: AGU. Available at: <https://epic.awi.de/id/eprint/50806/> (Accessed: 21 March 2024).

Li, Q. *et al.* (no date) 'Soil carbon assimilation effectively constrains carbon-cycle model forecasting', *in prep* [Preprint].

Mathers, C. *et al.* (2023) 'Validating DayCent-CR for cropland soil carbon offset reporting at a national scale', *Geoderma*, 438, p. 116647. Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2023.116647>.

Melton, F.S. *et al.* (2022) 'OpenET: Filling a critical data gap in water management for the western United States', *Journal of the American Water Resources Association*, 58(6), pp. 971–994. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1752-1688.12956>.

Nevalainen, O. *et al.* (2022) 'Towards agricultural soil carbon monitoring, reporting, and verification through the Field Observatory Network (FiON)', *Geoscientific Instrumentation Methods and Data Systems*, 11(1), pp. 93–109. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5194/gi-11-93-2022>.

Poggio, L. *et al.* (2021) 'SoilGrids 2.0: producing soil information for the globe with quantified spatial uncertainty', *SOIL*, 7(1), pp. 217–240. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5194/soil-7-217-2021>.

Raczka, B. *et al.* (2021) 'Improving CLM5.0 Biomass and Carbon Exchange Across the Western United States Using a Data Assimilation System', *Journal of advances in modeling earth systems*, 13(7), p. e2020MS002421. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020MS002421>.

Raiho, A. *et al.* (2020) 'Towards understanding predictability in ecology: A forest gap model case study', *bioRxiv*. bioRxiv. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.05.05.079871>.

Ramcharan, A. *et al.* (2018) 'Soil property and class maps of the conterminous United States at 100-meter spatial resolution', *Soil Science Society of America journal. Soil Science Society of America*, 82(1), pp. 186–201. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2017.04.0122>.

Reichle, R.H. *et al.* (2019) 'Version 4 of the SMAP level-4 soil moisture algorithm and data product', *Journal of advances in modeling earth systems*, 11(10), pp. 3106–3130. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019ms001729>.

Reichle, R.H. *et al.* (2021) 'Assimilation of SMAP Brightness Temperature Observations in the GEOS Land-Atmosphere Data Assimilation System', *IEEE journal of selected topics in applied earth observations and remote sensing*, 14, pp. 10628–10643. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/jstars.2021.3118595>.

Riemer, K. *et al.* (2024) *CCT Data Science Group Procedures*. Zenodo. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.10783692>.

Ross, R. *et al.* (2022) 'California Agriculture: Using Earth Observations to Estimate the Age and Carbon Stock of Perennial Agriculture'. Available at: <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/citations/20220006027> (Accessed: 20 March 2024).

Schlesinger, W.H. and Bernhardt, E.S. (2013) *Biogeochemistry: An Analysis of Global Change*. Academic Press. Available at: https://books.google.com/books/about/Biogeochemistry.html?hl=&id=533UOWBU3_AC.

Schnepf, A. *et al.* (2020) 'Call for Participation: Collaborative Benchmarking of Functional-Structural Root Architecture Models. The Case of Root Water Uptake', *Frontiers in plant science*, 11, p. 316. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2020.00316>.

Schnepf, A. *et al.* (2023) 'Collaborative benchmarking of functional-structural root architecture

models: Quantitative comparison of simulated root water uptake', *in silico Plants*, 5(1), p. diad005. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/insilicoplants/diad005>.

Soil Survey Staff (2023) 'Gridded Soil Survey Geographic (gSSURGO) Database for California'.

Takele, R. (2021) 'Global high-resolution gridded dataset of N₂O emission and mitigation potential (GhrdNEv1.0) from Maize and Wheat fields'. Mendeley. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.17632/HCVM3ZRB95.1>.

Tang, Y. *et al.* (2024) 'Quantifying greenhouse gas emissions in agricultural systems: a comparative analysis of process models', *Ecological modelling*, 490(110646), p. 110646. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2024.110646>.

Thompson, J.B. *et al.* (2023) 'Remote sensing of hedgerows, windbreaks, and winter cover crops in California's Central Coast reveals low adoption but hotspots of use', *Frontiers in sustainable food systems*, 7. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2023.1052029>.

Thompson, R., Patra, P. and Wilson, C. (2019) 'Global nitrous oxide fluxes estimated using atmospheric inversions'. Zenodo. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3384591>.

Thrasher, B. *et al.* (2022) 'NASA Global Daily Downscaled Projections, CMIP6', *Scientific data*, 9(1), p. 262. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01393-4>.

USDA NASS (2024) *Cropland Data Layer, CroplandCROS*. Washington, D.C.: USDA NASS Marketing and Information Services Office. Available at: <https://croplandcros.scinet.usda.gov/> (Accessed: 31 January 2024).

Verhoeven, E. *et al.* (2017) 'N₂O emissions from California farmlands: A review', *California Agriculture*, 71(3), pp. 148–159. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3733/ca.2017a0026>.

Wang, Q. *et al.* (2020) 'Data-driven estimates of global nitrous oxide emissions from croplands', *National science review*, 7(2), pp. 441–452. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/nsr/nwz087>.

Wheeler, K.I. and Dietze, M.C. (2019) 'A Statistical Model for Estimating Midday NDVI from the Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite (GOES) 16 and 17', *Remote Sensing*, 11(21), p. 2507. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11212507>.

Wheeler, K.I. and Dietze, M.C. (2021) 'Improving the monitoring of deciduous broadleaf phenology using the Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite (GOES) 16 and 17', *Biogeosciences*, 18(6), pp. 1971–1985. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-18-1971-2021>.

White, J.W. *et al.* (2013) 'Integrated description of agricultural field experiments and production: The ICASA Version 2.0 data standards', *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 96, pp. 1–12. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2013.04.003>.

Wieder, W.R. *et al.* (2021) 'SoDaH: the SOils DAta Harmonization database, an open-source synthesis of soil data from research networks, version 1.0', *Earth System Science Data*, 13(5), pp. 1843–1854. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-13-1843-2021>.

Zhang, M. *et al.* (2021) 'A MODIS-based scalable remote sensing method to estimate sowing and harvest dates of soybean crops in Mato Grosso, Brazil', *Heliyon*, 7(7), p. e07436. Available

at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e07436>.

Zhu, L. *et al.* (2019) 'Long-Term Monitoring of Cropland Change near Dongting Lake, China, Using the LandTrendr Algorithm with Landsat Imagery', *Remote Sensing*, 11(10), p. 1234. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11101234>.

Zhu, Z. and Woodcock, C.E. (2014) 'Continuous change detection and classification of land cover using all available Landsat data', *Remote Sensing of the Environment*, 144, pp. 152–171. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2014.01.011>.

Zobitz, J.M. *et al.* (2008) 'Integration of process-based soil respiration models with whole-ecosystem CO₂ measurements', *Ecosystems*, 11(2), pp. 250–269. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10021-007-9120-1>.

Required Attachments

The required attachments provided in pages 46-76 of the proposal include various forms and certifications that are not included in the archival copy. Attachments excluded from archive include:

- Attachment 1: Required Attachment Checklist
- Attachment 3: Proposer References Form
- Attachment 4: Payee Data Record (STD 204)
- Attachment 6: Contractor Certification Clauses (CCC 04/2017)
- Attachment 7: California Civil Rights Laws Certification
- Attachment 8: Darfur Contracting Act Certification
- Attachment 9: Bidder Declaration GSPD-05-105
- Attachment 12: Detailed Response for Minimum Qualifications
- Attachment 13: COVID-19 Prevention Contractor Self-Certification
- Attachment 14: Conflict of Interest & Confidentiality Statement